

ARTS

FAZIL SAY: TURKEY'S PIONEERING PIANIST-COMPOSER

Maikovskaia A.

Bachelor degree

*Özgün Çocuklar Montessori Anaokulu School
Madenler Mah. Kurukaya Sk. No: 24, Istanbul, Turkey
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10974896>*

Abstract

This article explores the life and career of Fazıl Say, a renowned Turkish musician known for his contributions as a pianist and composer. Born into a family deeply rooted in Turkish art and music, Say's upbringing in an intellectually stimulating environment laid the groundwork for his artistic journey. His initial musical training under Mithat Fenmen in Turkey, followed by further education in Germany, equipped him with a profound classical foundation, while his improvisational skills highlighted his unique musical style. Say's rise to fame was marked by significant international achievements and accolades, enhancing his reputation across classical and jazz genres. His recordings, particularly of classical masterworks and his own compositions, have been critically acclaimed. Say's work not only demonstrates his technical mastery and innovative approach but also reflects his deep connection to Turkish cultural heritage. Through his compositions and performances, he acts as a bridge between traditional Turkish music and global musical influences, embodying the fusion of cultural identity and artistic expression. This article illustrates how Say's career epitomizes the synthesis of personal heritage with a broader artistic panorama, positioning him as a pivotal figure in the modern musical landscape.

Keywords: Fazıl Say, Turkish musician, pianist and composer, classical and jazz music, cultural heritage, improvisational skills, international recognition, music education, artistic influence, cross-cultural fusion, symphony compositions, musical innovation, family background in arts, international awards, recording achievements.

Family Background and Early Influences

Fazıl Say was born on January 14, 1970, in Ankara, Turkey. He comes from a family with a strong background in Turkish art, especially academic painting. His grandmother, Zehra Say (1906–1990), was a well-known Turkish painter and a symbol of the Atatürk era. She fought for equality and passed on her love for art to her daughter, Emel Say, who also became a professional painter. Fazıl's father, Ahmet Say, was a respected musicologist.

Growing up in this artistic and intellectual environment shaped Fazıl Say's path into the world of art. His roles as a composer and performer fit naturally into the rich history of Turkish musical culture. His journey shows a deep, personal connection to 20th-century art, continuing his family's legacy in music.

Rise to Fame and Musical Education

Fazıl Say quickly became known as a talented pianist and composer in the 1990s. He won many competitions and performed with top orchestras around the world. He also made a name for himself in the jazz world, playing at international jazz festivals and showing his ability to succeed in different styles of music.

Say's musical journey began in Turkey, where he learned from Mithat Fenmen (1916–1982), a well-known Turkish composer and pianist. Fenmen taught Say the basics of piano playing and composition, which would be important for his future work. Fenmen himself had studied with Nadia Boulanger and improved his piano skills with Alfred Cortot at the Paris Conservatory. This rich educational background gave Say a strong artistic foundation and inspired him to keep learning and creating.

Mithat Fenmen saw the early talent in his student and encouraged Fazıl Say to improvise every day, focusing on themes that interested him before any structured lessons. This unusual approach to music education allowed Say to be creative and free, which helped develop his impressive improvisational skills and unique style. These early experiences with experimentation and exploration played a big role in shaping Say into an original and thoughtful pianist and composer.

Education and International Recognition

Say continued his education at the Ankara Conservatory, which combines Turkish and European musical traditions. The involvement of Paul Hindemith, an important German musician, in starting the conservatory is especially noteworthy. Hindemith worked to change music education in Turkey and created the "Universal Educational Program of Turkish Polyphonic Music". This helped bridge cultural differences and made the conservatory a place where future generations of Turkish musicians could grow.

Fazıl Say's musical journey then took him to Germany, where he received a scholarship to study at the Robert Schumann Hochschule in Düsseldorf with pianist David Levine, focusing on both piano performance and composition. He continued his studies with Levine in Berlin. From 1990 to 1994, Say began to gain recognition in the international music scene as a very talented and genuine performer.

Say's success in the American music world started with his win at the International Young Concert Artists Competition in New York in 1994. This victory showed his skill and talent as an artist. It also marked the beginning of his influence in the United States, with later performances at important venues like New York and the

Kennedy Center in Washington. In 1995, he won the Beracasa Foundation Award, which led to more international recognition and performances, such as at the International Radio France Festival in Montpellier. In December 2016, he was honored with the International Beethoven Prize in Bonn for his dedication to human rights, peace, and freedom. In 2017, the City of Duisburg in Germany recognized his contributions to music with its Music Prize.

Recordings and Collaborations

Say's recordings of classical works by J.S. Bach, Mozart, Beethoven, Gershwin, and Stravinsky, as well as his performances of Mussorgsky and his own compositions, have received praise from critics and multiple ECHO Klassik Awards. Since 2016, he has worked exclusively with Warner Classics, producing important recordings like a complete collection of Mozart sonatas, which earned him an ECHO Klassik in 2017. His "4 Cities" project with Nicolas Altstaedt, his edition of Chopin's Nocturnes and Secrets (French songs) recorded with Marianne Crebass (mezzo-soprano) won the Gramophone Classical Music Award in 2018.

His 2018 album focuses on the music of Debussy and Satie, while F. Say's latest CD edition, Troy Sonata – Fazil Say Plays Say, includes only the composer's original works.

Say performs with orchestras all over the world, including the New York Philharmonic, the Vienna Symphony Orchestra, Concertgebouw Orchestra, BBC Philharmonic Orchestra, National Orchestra of France under the direction of many leading conductors. He plays a mix of Viennese classics and 20th-century masterpieces. Known for his strong stage presence, Say has been dubbed a "genius" by the *Le Figaro* newspaper, highlighting his influence on the international music scene. He also works with other chamber music musicians, in particular with violinists Patricia Copacinska (a Swiss violinist of Moldovan origin) and Maxim Vengerov (a famous violinist), demonstrating his mastery in various genres of music.

In addition, the musician has established himself as a brilliant stage artist - not just a performer, but a musician of outstanding artistic talent, which is manifested in relevant artistry, which is expressed in countless photographs and videos from F. Sai's concerts.

Compositions and Cultural Heritage

As a composer, Say's work is very diverse. He writes solo piano pieces, concertos, orchestral works, and music for ballet and film. His compositions often include themes that reflect his cultural background. His "First Symphony - Istanbul" is a good example of this, combining his new compositional voice with elements that show his strong connection to his roots.

Say's ability to perform and compose makes him an important figure in modern music. He brings together different cultures and styles with a unique vision that touches both the heart and the mind.

Symphonic Works and Solo Compositions

Fazil Say's symphonies take listeners on a journey through rich cultural and historical stories.

For instance, the complete list of his symphonic works includes:

(Symphony No. 1) – "Istanbul Symphony" (Op. 28),

(Symphony No. 2) – "Mesopotamia Symphony" (No. 2, Op. 38),

(Symphony No. 3) – "Universe Symphony" (No. 3, Op. 43), "1914" (Op. 56),

"Four Preludes" for saxophone quartet and string orchestra with percussion (Op. 63),

"Symphonic Dances" (Op. 64),

"Grand Bazaar" (Rhapsody for Symphony Orchestra, Op. 65).

His compositions for solo instruments with orchestra are even more diverse:

Three Marches for Piano and Chamber Orchestra (no opus number)

,Symphonic Concertante for Piano with Orchestra (Op. 3),

Guitar Concerto (Op. 5),

"Hayam Concerto" for Clarinet with Orchestra (Op. 36),

"Hezarfen Concerto" for Ney with Orchestra (Op. 39),

Concerto for Trumpet with Orchestra (Op. 31),

"Thousand and One Nights" Violin Concerto (Op. 25),

Two Romantic Ballads for Piano and String Orchestra (1995),

"Nirvana Explosion" – Concert Piece for Piano with Orchestra (Op. 30),

"Thinking Einstein" – Concert Piece for Piano with Orchestra (Op. 16),

"Silence of Anatolia" (Piano Concerto No. 3, Op. 11).

Artistic Evolution and Cultural Fusion

Fazil Say's artistic path combines different musical traditions and a strong commitment to trying new things. His early years studying with Mithat Fenmen gave him a foundation in classical music and also planted the seeds for a spirit of exploration, especially in improvisation. This early exposure to creative freedom became a key part of Say's musical identity, which would grow when he experienced American culture. The U.S., with its lively jazz scene, gave Say a place to develop as an artist and sparked a deep interest and involvement in jazz. Starting the Worldjazz quartet in 2000 and playing in places from Montpellier to jazz festivals in Montreux and Istanbul show his flexibility and genuine love for jazz, which can also be seen in his jazz-inspired improvisations and compositions.

Say's journey shows a special mix of cultural identities and artistic fields. His work is not just about his own achievements but also serves as a link between Turkish and European musical landscapes. His active role in both worlds shows a deep commitment to adding to the musical tapestry with his unique voice and vision. Say's work goes beyond traditional boundaries, drawing from a rich well of cultural heritage while embracing global influences.

Moreover, Say's artistic philosophy is deeply rooted in a sense of national pride and historical awareness. His engagement with Turkish history and culture is not just academic but a heartfelt commitment to celebrating and promoting his heritage. This dedication

can be seen in his works that draw from Turkish themes and in his support for the importance of national culture. Through his music, Say invites a conversation about identity, history, and the transformative power of art.

In Say's work, we see a musician who is not only a master of his craft but also an ambassador of cultural exchange and understanding. His story is one of continuity and change, where the echoes of the past meet the innovations of the present. Fazıl Say stands as a guide for future generations, showing how tradition and modernity can come together in the service of artistic expression and cultural pride. His life and work represent the journey of a musician deeply engaged with the world around him, committed to exploring the vast possibilities of music while staying connected to the rich soil of his cultural heritage.

Continuing a Venerable Tradition

Fazıl Say positions himself as a modern carrier of a respected tradition that combines the roles of performer and composer—a lineage that includes great names such as J.S. Bach, D. Scarlatti, W.A. Mozart, and L. van Beethoven. This lineage continued through the 19th century with giants like F. Chopin, F. Liszt, J. Brahms, N. Rubinstein, and into the 20th century with S.V. Rachmaninoff, A. Scriabin, N. Medtner, S. Prokofiev. Say's embodiment of this dual heritage shows a historical continuity within European musical traditions, showcasing the combination of creative performance and composition within a single artist.

In Say's wide-ranging repertoire, one finds a mix that spans time periods and genres - from Baroque keyboard masterpieces to his own modern jazz improvisations. His improvisation on the theme from W.A. Mozart's Piano Sonata in A major K. 331 ("Turkish March") has especially resonated, crossing cultural boundaries to become a symbol of modern Turkey, despite its European origins. Additionally, Say's transcription of J.S. Bach's Fantasy in G minor (BWV 542) and his jazz interpretation of Paganini's 24th Caprice are examples of his artistic versatility and deep engagement with the musical past.

Say's highly skilled performance style has captivated audiences worldwide and earned critical praise. His strategic inclusion of original compositions in concert programs gives him a unique place in the musical landscape, free from competition and fully in line with his artistic vision. This special blend of originality and tradition has not only helped him appear on major global stages but also established his status as one of Turkey's most prominent musical figures.

A strong passion for Turkish musical culture fills Say's creative work. His compositions often draw upon national themes, and when arranging works by other composers, he chooses those with important ties to Turkish culture. When adapting material by others, Say skillfully weaves Turkish musical styles with elements from European and jazz traditions, enriching his works with a distinctive national character.

While not all of Say's piano compositions openly engage with Turkish history or culture, many are filled with a sense of national identity, partly due to his skilled use of improvisation - a technique deeply rooted in Turkish folk music. This national essence is shown both in the musical language and the themes of his works, promising further exploration in future discussions. This exploration into Fazıl Say's work reveals a musician deeply committed to fostering a dialogue between his cultural heritage and a broader musical world, championing a blend of tradition and innovation that continues to resonate across the global music scene.

References:

1. Asafiev, B. V. [Text]: scientific collection / R. G. Shitikova // About the music of the XX century. - Moscow, 1982. - Pages 57-77.
2. Belyaev V. M. Turkish music [text] / V. Belyaev. - M.: Sov. music, 1934, No. 5. — P. 56.
3. Gavrilova N. A. On the problem of nationality in the music of the twentieth century [text] / N. Gavrilova // Scientific. works of the Moscow State Conservatory named after. P.I. Tchaikovsky. Manuals on the history of foreign music. Vol. 1. - M.: Moscow Conservatory, 2003. -136 p.
4. Drozhzhina M. N. East-West: two types of reconstruction in the context of the composer-folklore problem [text] // Musical culture as a national and world phenomenon: Materials of the international scientific conference. - Novosibirsk, 2002. - P. 255-263.
5. Zehra Say // Portal of Turkish literature [electronic source]. Access mode: <https://edebiyatvesanat akademisi.com/turk-ressamlar/zehra-say-2319.aspx> (access date: 27/03/2024).
6. Jurgen Otten: Piyanist - Besteci - Dunya Yurt-tasi: Fazıl Say [text] / — 1-th edition. — Berlin: Henschel, 2011. — 176 page.
7. F. Say // Official website of the publishing house "SchottMusic" [electronic source]. Access mode: <https://en.schott-music.com/shop/autoren/fazl-say> (access date: 20/03/2024).
8. F. Say and the classical music scene as an informal learning space [electronic source] // EuropäischeHochschulschriften / Research of European Universities / Publications... Musicology / Series 36: Musicology // Taschenbuckh, 2010. Access mode: <https://www.amazon.de/Europäische-Hochschulschriften-University-Publications-Musicology/dp/3631612486/>(access date: 24/03/2024).
9. Mazel, L. A. Problems of classical harmony [Text] : monograph / L. A. Mazel. - Moscow: Music, 1972. - 616 page.
10. Kholopov, Yu.N. Scriabin [Text]: monograph / Yu.N. Kholopov //Essays on Modern Harmony. - Moscow: Music, 1974. - Pages 188 - 200.
11. Kholopov, Yu. N. Harmony. Practical course [Text]: a textbook for special courses of conservatories (musicology and composition departments): in 2 parts, Part 2 / Yu. N. Kholopov. - Moscow: Publishing house "Composer", 2003. - Pages 170-178.